

SMART SECONDARY SUBSTATION DEVELOPMENT AND DEMONSTRATION UNDER FLEXIGRID PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

This paper starts explaining FLEXIGRID project goals and expected results in order to understand the global scope of the project. Afterwards, it will focus on a particular objective focused on Secondary Substation grid automation and control use case from the Spanish DEMO. There, the three main electrical components of a Secondary Substation such as Medium Voltage Switchgear, OLTC transformer and the Low Voltage Board show novelties developed along the project and that were tested on field during last year. To end the paper and taking advantage of a full year of data, the paper will go deep in the analysis of the contribution of the transformers automatic tap changer towards grid stability while renewable energy generation resources are present.

INTRODUCTION

FLEXIGRID (Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic FLEXibility services in the distribution GRID) is a research project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon H2020 programme. The main goal of FLEXIGRID is to allow the distribution grid to operate in a secure and stable manner when a large share of variable generation electricity sources are connected to low and medium voltage grids.

To do so, FLEXIGRID proposes a three-level approach aiming at (1) Flexibility, (2) Reliability, and (3) Economic Efficiency through the development of innovative hardware and software solutions.

These solutions will be demonstrated in four Demo-Sites across Europe (Croatia, Spain, Greece and Italy) ensuring their interoperability through their integration into an open source platform able to harmonize the data flow between FLEXIGRID solutions and the real grid.

FLEXIGRID Specific Goals

The following eight points summarize Flexigrid specific goals:

1: improve the power system flexibility, enhancing the grid hosting capacity of RES through DR, P2X, storage of electricity and variable generation towards the energy network decarbonisation.

2: increase the observability, controllability and

automation of the network systems for the improvement of both the security and resilience of the grid.

3: mitigate short-term and long-term congestions in the distribution grid from an economic efficient point of view thus reducing the cost of the European energy transition.

4: ensure the interoperability and compatibility of the developed solutions with the different platforms used by the European DSOs guaranteeing a proper and secure data management.

5: carry out a complete demonstration program up to TRL 8 in four different demo-sites, obtaining reliable results on its replicability and ensuring its attractiveness for European stakeholders.

6: identify and analyze the needs and shortfalls of the distribution grid as well as the obstacles to innovation under the current local and international context and regulation framework.

7: raise awareness among citizens and other relevant stakeholders of the transition towards a low carbon economy considering them as active players in the energy system.

8: ensure the exploitation of the project results by developing a corresponding business plan as well as their dissemination by exchanging knowledge with other projects under the BRIDGE Initiative.

EXPECTED RESULTS/IMPACTS

The projects seeks to improve stability and flexibility, reducing SAIDI and SAIFI, as well as the curtailment decrease thanks to the improvement of the observability and control over the grid.

Reduction of the reinforcement of interconnections and investments needed to maintain the quality and stability of the grid, improving the capability to manage future energy loads.

CO2 emissions savings due to the larger penetration of share RES, contributing to the 2030 Climate-Energy objectives.

SMART SECONDARY SUBSTATION

Multiple developments have been performed in each of the main electrical components of the Secondary Substation, that will allow a better time of response, autonomous control and flexibility in the grid.

Automated Medium Voltage Switchgears are more and more deployed over the grid with a clear goal to improve quality of service. The electronic components of the solution such as RTUs or fault detectors are continuously under development so new firmware releases are commonly available over the years. If already deployed Secondary Substations need to be upgraded with new releases, up to now one by one upgrades were doable locally or remotely, but this tasks gets tedious when the number of installation is high. To solve this issue, web services were developed to allow massive upgrades easily [1]. Once the basis of web services is developed for firmware upgrades, other services were also considered and developed to increase the functionalities. Thus, the following were developed in the project:

- MV Automation status: it allows to have a brief summary of the status of the installation and it also serves as an inventory of the electronic devices.
- Reception of MV Automation events: it allows to receive the events if the installation.
- RTU_MV firmware update: it allows to upgrade the firmware remotely.

Figure 1: MV Automated switchgear

Another novelty related to MV switchgears was the introduction of a digital sensor to measure the internal pressure of the switchgears. This allows to have a numerical value of the pressure that can be exchange even remotely and serves as input for health index purposes.

As a second electrical component, an intelligent Low Voltage Board has been designed [2] following IEC 61439 standard to achieve safe operation conditions, including arc fault tested in accordance with IEC/TR 61641.

Figure 2: Intelligent Low Voltage Board

Each three-phase feeder has an electronic devices to monitor the status of the Low Voltage line measuring voltage and current through current transformers. Electrical parameters are thus measured giving the possibility to save Low Voltage load profile, as well as disturbances such as over or under voltages. Blown fuse detection algorithm is also implemented to be able to send alarms to dispatch centres.

A LV RTU retrieves all the information before sending the information to the system, where many applications could be implemented thanks to all the exchanged information to improve network planning and maintenance operations.

As a part of the development, a definition of:

- Standardized exchanged data sets and signals.
- Integration of the exchanged information through MV RTU.
- Definition of secondary signaling and alarms for its integration into Webservices.

Lastly, a new compact intelligent distribution transformer [3] with an on-load tap changer (OLTC) capable of automatically regulating the voltage, to deal with fluctuations generated by new loads and variable DG in the LV network as well as compensating Medium Voltage instabilities in the MV network.

Based on an electromechanical OLTC that can change the tap position automatically and under load. The new smart distribution transformer can increase the hosting capacity of LV network without the need for new infrastructure.

From the intelligent transformer control point of view, a new IED is developed [4]. Among all the functions available, the following can be mentioned:

- Peak and transmission to the dispatch centre of all low voltage measurements.
- Control the tap changes of the smart transformer.
- Receive and set the voltage set point for the smart transformer.

In terms of standardization of the control equipment of the intelligent distribution transformer, the same work as for the Low Voltage Board electronics has been made:

- Standardized exchanged data sets and signals.
- Integration of the exchanged information through MV RTU.
- Definition of secondary signaling and alarms for its integration into Webservices.

OLTC BASED TRANSFORMER PERFORMANCE DATA ANALYSIS

The Spanish DEMO is connected to the 12kV network system in a line with several photovoltaic generators in Low Voltage (LV). That is the reason to be the final candidate for such a project.

The Renewable Power (RP) level connected at this point is (46%). The following figure shows an example of Energy (kW) monitored along the study time at the secondary winding of the distribution transformer installed.

Figure 3: Energy exported/imported measured at the distribution transformer secondary (LV)

The RP presence is noticeable and, therefore, the possible effect over LV stability at the end customers. It is one of the most relevant points to be analyzed. And how the OLTC technology can stabilize LV and avoid voltage levels out of national regulations.

The main characteristics of the installed transformer.smart are (12kV/420V, 250KVA) with an OLTC (On Load Tap Changer) according to taps regulation ($\pm 2 \pm 4 \pm 6 \pm 8 \pm 10 \pm 12$). The the tap change control is performed by the IED.

Figure 4: OLTC based transformer

This control box measures the complete three phase system in order to have a perfect image of the voltage variations and consider the possible phase unbalance, instead of a single phase measurement. The OLTC tap position is also physically monitored by digital inputs.

Figure 5: OLTC based transformer controller

All the OLTC system information (voltage measurements, oil temperatura/level/pressure alarms, active tap, UP/DOWN commands, ...) is remotely accessible in real time by IEC 60870-5-104 communication protocol to the utility's SCADA system. All the parameters and records of control box are also remotely accessible by WEB server.

Throughout the experimentation time, OLTC has made 2,157 automatic tap changes since its commissioning on 28th October 2021 until 2th February 2022. On 26th April 2022 it has 3,041 changes. In total, we are talking about 16 changes per day on average.

The following figures shows an example of this regulation and how it is possible to stabilize the LV grid by means of tap changes of the transformer.

Figure 6: Voltage stabilization by means of OLTC changes.

Low Voltage phases at the transformer secondary winding are identified with (V1, V2, V3). Limit MAX/MIN values indicate the stabilization objective. SETPOINT value indicates the voltage target.

It is also indicated with a number the active tap position, just before a new change of the OLTC position.

Along all these changes, LV is always within the voltage range expected and defined as a parameter in OLTC control to be maintained. In another words, OLTC avoids the effect of RP on LV stability.

CONCLUSIONS

The paper has presented various developments performed inside Flexigrid project for Secondary Substations use case. As general conclusions, the following could be stated:

- Secondary Substation digitalization has been increased, thus obtaining more functionality per installed asset.
- Standardization of the Data exchanged with central dispatch centres has been defined per electrical component.
- New data sets and signalling are available at the MV RTU, LV RTU and OLTC transformer controller.
- Web services development will improve the response time, increase efficiency when deploying new functionalities and allow access to the information of the Secondary substation for non real time applications too.
- SAIDI and SAIFI are improved due to increased

automation, as well as the reduction of power outages thanks to the improvement of the observability and control over the grid.

Regarding the analysis of the data obtained during the test period of the Flexigrid project for the OLTC transformer, results show the correct operation of the smart transformer installed with OLTC technology, showing the improvement of the stability and flexibility of the electrical grid, even with the presence of DEG.

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